

Long Term Impact of Higher Education on Pak-China Relations: Focusing on Educational Exchange Policies

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: April 25, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: November 29, 2021</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Educational Exchange, Economic Growth, Strategies And Planning, Promoting, Strengthening</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5737442</p>	<p><i>Educational exchange and its impact on economic growth and development depend both on the short term and long term strategies and planning. Higher education institution, in this globalised world has emerged as a major player in international relations. Therefore, Higher education Commission plays important role in promoting, strengthening and diversifying relations between China and Pakistan. China-Pakistan Economic Corridor (CPEC) has commenced as a huge project by Pakistan and China. Moreover, it was considered as a “game changer” for both the countries to promote free trade and enhance economic growth. However, under CPEC generating numerous business and employment prospects for local citizens has only been focused theoretically. While, both the countries collaborate in a number of sectors especially defense, trade, energy sector and economic, however, its most important linkage with education is limited. Consequently, both the states have to focus on the academia. It could be considered as a major prosperity tool which can help both the states understand each other. Moreover, short, medium or long term educational exchange policies needs to be developed in order to present each other’s strengths and to prove as a tool to interpret the vision of a knowledge-based economy reality. This research formulates higher educational strategies to unleash utmost benefits from CPEC. Furthermore, it fills the gap and inspects the possible outcomes of CPEC for local citizens of Pakistan through training and educational exchange policies. Additionally, this paper will focus on achieving long term social and economic objectives from long, medium and short term Higher education Commission of both the states in the light of social exchange theory.</i></p>

Introduction

Globally transformation of education, financing to knowledge based economy and implementation of customaries approach from manufacturing has stressed on institutions as well as countries to devise numerous retention approach for surviving in international education market. Such approaches resulted in several countries ending up in opening their borders to international students in order to enter into a competitive environment.

China-Pakistan Economic Corridor (CPEC) has commenced a huge project by promoting free trade and economic growth. CPEC is considered by government officials and policymakers as a game changer for both the states. Consequently, promoting various employment opportunities and generating businesses for local populace plus global outreach. Moreover, CPEC projects needs to get support and awareness from the locals communities to get smooth implementation.

Since China has taken up reform and open door policies in 1978, both Pakistan and China continued to take their relations forward whereas previously their relations were limited to generally inter-governmental contact and narrow people-to-people interactions. Pakistan and China considers each others as the most reliable neighbor and trust worthy partners. However, till 2007, in China there was no particular Pakistan research centre or institution. Meanwhile, Pakistan’s government felt the need to support Chinese universities to establish a number of focused research institutions promoting Pakistan studies in China.

First Pakistan Studies Centre in China was established in April 2007, the Pakistan culture and communication Study Centre at Tsinghua University in 2008. This Center at Tsinghua University is principally engaged in enhancing Pakistani culture associated research. Furthermore, it also focused on designing academic exchange activities for further expanding mutual exchanges and collaboration in the field of cultural diffusion. Resultantly, boosting mutual understanding of culture, history and further advancing the partnership and friendship between both the states.

The early work by Homans focused on the relationships of group members and on such issues as influence and conformity. Blau (1964) discussed how the need for advice or help leads to exchanges among members in groups and organizations. The person providing assistance (cost) is rewarded with respect, esteem, or some

reciprocal action from the advisee. Repeated advising interactions can be the foundation of a relationship even when assistance is no longer needed. For the relationship to continue, an equitable exchange of rewards is required.

Social Exchange Theory:

American sociologist George Homans originated social exchange theory by publishing an article in 1958, entitled "Social Behavior as Exchange." He in that article created a framework constructed on a combination of basic economics and behaviorism. Meanwhile, gradually other studies enhanced further the parameter of fundamental concepts of Homans' work.

The basic concept of Social exchange theory is built on the perception that an association or relation between two parties or people is formed through a procedure of cost and benefit examination. In addition, it is designed in a way to determine the effort pour in by an individual or parties in their relationship.

This theory relies basically on systematic process of logic and mathematics instead of emotions to determine balance within a relationship. This theory can be applied to determine the balance within a friendship and can also be used to gauge idealistic relationships. Hence, with a view to enhance Chinese and Pakistani mutual collaboration by involvement of Higher Education Commissions of both the states, Social Exchange theory seems an appropriate tool.

This world is engaged in numerous exchanges on every day basis with a broad variety of actors most often implanted in the networks, groups, institutions and organizations we inhabit. That is why, exchange theory remained as a major theoretical perspectives on social structure and social interaction.

Basic Assumptions of Social Exchange Theory:

There are some thoughts regarding Social Exchange Theory, they are: parties involved in social Exchange Theory logically quest for maximizing their profits. They believe that exchanges bring more profitable situations as compared to their present ones as people from different places have exposure to diverse information about social, economic, and psychological aspects. Similarly, different people allow the alternative doors to be considered. Moreover, people are more goals oriented in such free competitive system. Those individuals who feel deprived in terms of such procedure will value the opportunity and would come out with better outcome. Furthermore, in rewarding situation (offered by Social Exchange) people become more rational and determine the promising means to compete.

Educational Exchange Programe as a modality of Public diplomacy:

Globalization, bought revolution in communications and technology, resultantly, people across the globe are more closely connected than ever. People are now updated with the News and lifestyles from the readily available information. Furthermore, Social media platforms enlighten the public who in return exert power and have an ability to exercise influence on their particular governments.

any part of the world are accessible to anyone with an internet connection. Today's public,

In the modern era, diplomats have to compete with a massive amount of networks and non-state actors who surpass the limits of Westphalian nation states. In such situation traditional diplomacy becomes no longer an adequate modality to carry out foreign policy. Therefore, a state must develop substitute paths to influence and exert itself in the world as a soft power. Public diplomacy, is that aspect of foreign policy which is concerned with the psychological or human facade of international relations.

Taking part in student exchange programs at university level could be an unmatched chance for growth and learning. Educational exchanges expose students to foreign languages, cultures, and traditions. There are various programs designed for language interests, other programs have semester or yearlong education as their ambition. Students can participate in exchange through pre-arranged high school programs, commercial student exchange services, or university study abroad offices.

It is its purpose, which characterizes an exchange program. There are certain student exchange programs which are designed mainly for cultural exposure, while others are designed for education. They could be planned to either sharpen students' foreign language skills or to throw light on international issues like, poverty and hunger in Africa, violation of human rights in Asia or environmental degradation in Central and South and Central America.

governments in such a way as to exercise influence over anticipation to promote constructive images of one's country and lessen misunderstandings, activities like cultural their foreign policy decisions" ("Definitions of Public Diplomacy", n.d.). Through a set of today, states must develop alternative avenues to influence and wield "soft" power as propounded by Joseph Nye (1990). Soft power according to Nye is, "the ability to get what you nooks, disseminatnation strategies and educational exchange programs engage states in public diplomacy activities. Educational exchanges are meant to absolutely influence and exert a pull on the other states in order to gather support for their foreign policies. Whilst, it is an attempt to arise positive

perceptive for its nation's ideas and ideals. Its institutions and culture, as well as its national goals and current policies" (p. 3). Many states in today's world are using student's exchange program as a tool for enhancing their influence and promote their international policy agendas. Furthermore, Governments plays an active role in sending and getting students among their institutes of higher education.

Long & Short-Term Education plan:

The objectives and target for which the long & short-term plans are designed, they very successfully results in a series of promising format. The set of principles which may help in having potential long & short-term planning process are:

- Building, practicing and applying skills
- The learning procedure
- Evolution through stages and leading towards independence.

Hence, the objectives of the short term educational exchange projects between Pakistan and China are for the purpose of creating alliance amongst the CPEC Consortium Universities, to study the geo-economic and geo-strategic scope of the Chinese Belt and Road initiative (BRI) and CPEC to enhance and gain the long-term results of mutual collaboration between China and Pakistan.

Economic Engagement Generate Educational Exchanges:

Under CPEC, the growing economic binding between Pakistan and China partnership has grown deeper in the education sector. Moreover, Pakistan's and Chinese rising economic ties have laid the foundation for joint ventures in the education sector. Additionally, the demand for learning Chinese language, especially among middle class Pakistani youth is increasing. Resultantly, China has become a leading destination for higher education for Pakistani youth. That is why government of China has significantly extended scholarships for Pakistani students. Nevertheless, factors such as more affordable Chinese universities, greater awareness of Chinese higher education and growing confidence in the value of Chinese degree programs are behind the enhancement in enrollment of Pakistani students there. The main three rudiments of Chinese educational support not only for Pakistan but also for other developing countries are: vocational training programs, university scholarships and Chinese language courses. These partnerships have resulted from the Chinese government's thrust feature and Pakistan's pulls feature which is deep rooted in local environment. Moreover, these pull factors from Pakistan are based on the belief that Pakistan's closer ties with China would yield future political and economic returns as China is emerging as a global power.

Likewise, numerous Pakistanis have developed a mindset that they probably grow economic profits from studying in Chinese institutions of higher education rather than in the West. There has been a rapid increase in the number of Pakistani residents learning Chinese language at educational levels like schools (both middle & high), colleges and universities*. Meanwhile, Pakistani elites keeps looking at the West as their preferred target for higher education however, the Pakistani middle class are gradually more inclined towards Chinese universities. Apart from the growing economic and societal relationships between Pakistan and China, the major reason behind this growing trend of joining Chinese Universities, is the lesser cost of higher education in China. Nevertheless, the cost of taking higher education in Western universities likes United States or United Kingdom (UK) etc are comparatively high.

The demand for Chinese language classes in Pakistan is growing. China time and again reacting to demands from Pakistani universities has persistently kept sponsoring Confucius Institutes and classrooms all over the country. Furthermore, these institutes are designed alongside the outline of UK's British Council and France's Alliance Française. Moreover, there are about five Confucius Institutes working mainly in Punjab, one institution each in Sindh and in Islamabad. Whereas, emphasizing on cultural promotion and language training, China promotes a significant component of its aim to promote Chinese language, its image as soft power, enhancing local knowledge of Chinese traditions and culture and hence, organizing cultural exchanges.

The future of a State depends upon the kind of education they give to their children. Similarly, the future of Pakistan depends on the brought up of the future citizens of Pakistan. Therefore, by providing sound education, integrity, responsibility, implanting high sense of honor and selfless service to the nation we can flourish our future. That is why an instant and imperative need for giving technical and scientific education to the people of Pakistan is needed to enhance our prospect economic life. Additionally, better and modern education would make our people take to commerce, science, trade and mainly well-planned industry. Hence, it is critical to realize that we have to compete with the very fast moving world. However, the Education Sector in Pakistan is suffering from inadequate financial put in, poor quality of management/ supervision/ monitoring, low levels of efficiency for implementation of programs, and, and teaching. Chinese Government gives priority to the

* Bacha.Umar. *More Students in Pakistan are learning Chinese today than ever before.* (Dawn News. 22nd May, 2017).

<https://www.dawn.com/news/1333509/more-students-in-pakistan-are-learning-chinese-today-than-ever-before>

financial investment in education. Resultantly, Chinese expenditure for education of international standards is increasing. China is moving from a big educator to a greater one. Chinese Ministry of Education in 2010, issued the China's Medium-and Long-Term Talent Development Plan (2010-2020) where some strategic goals for education were proposed. Objective of this proposal was basically to achieve the transformation of education by 2020 like: formulating a learning oriented society, a boost in the efficiency of human resource. Additionally, it requires developing education equality in relation to the entire population, elevating general schooling to a higher one, providing high-class education, building a comprehensive education system for complete education and making an ideal education system. It further proposed some policies for higher education, like, those engaged in prominent research should be encouraged for opening up to the world and to support them to join and set up international academic collaboration organizations. Likewise, to build and hold up joint services with overseas research and education organizations at a high level, cultivating a collection of elite modernized talent, introducing world-class universities, establishment of a world-class curriculum, achieving a set of leading original achievements and utilizing every Yang Yingyu 271 efforts to toughen complete national effectiveness. Hence, it necessitates amplifying the number of international students in China, increasing the amount of sponsorship by the government of China. The major emphasis of this policy is on international students coming from developing countries. Presently, students from Pakistan are studying 100 in Bachelors, 3,600 in Masters, about 6,156 in Phd, and 3,000 in Short Term Exchange Programs in China.

As a response to the World Education Forum (26-28 April 2000, Dakar) where Dakar Framework for Action was adopted, Pakistan decided to develop an inclusive National Plan of Action (NPA) on Education for All. This plan was formulated as a framework (2001-15) and it had to be implemented in three phases on the span of five years. This framework focused on three of its focal points they were: early year's education, general primary education and adult literacy. However, due to lack of funds this plan failed to be executed. Under this plan and in coherence with the constitution and key policy framework, provinces will be introducing projects for the enhancement of the education sector. For the children, it ensured to provide equal, free, complete and compulsory primary education of good quality till 2015. For the adults, the target was to attain 50% enhancement in adult literacy by 2015 and eradicating gender inequality in primary and secondary education by 2005. Particularly, it emphasized more on guaranteeing female's equal access to and attainment in basic education of good quality. However, the outcome of this policy was also not fruitful. Thus, leaving Pakistan with the option of collaboration and coordination with the Higher Education and research commission of friendly states by designing short and long term exchanges to achieve long term goals of mutual assistance as well as flow of educated youth in the country.

The President of the People's Republic of China issued an order No.7 on August 29, 1998, under which the Higher Education Law of the People's Republic of China was concluded. The Article 12, in general provisions states that:

"The State encourages collaboration between higher education institutions and their collaboration with research institutes, enterprises and institutions in order that they all can draw on each other's strengths and increase the efficiency of educational resources. The State encourages and supports international exchange and cooperation in higher education."

Furthermore, article 36 in fourth chapter says that:

"Higher education institutions shall, in accordance with the relevant regulations of the State, act on their own in conducting exchange and co-operation with higher education institutions outside of the territory of China in the fields of science, technology and culture."

The Government of China gives great significance to interschool collaboration, it also promote universities to strengthen international cooperation. In addition to this, China ensures that the poorer students also get a higher quality education. Therefore, it has launched scholarships and encourages higher education enterprises, institutions, public organizations, groups and individuals to create scholarships in accordance with the appropriate regulations of the State. Moreover, China has also established work and study funds, loans for the students of higher education institutions. Likewise, it encourages higher education institutions, public organizations and individuals to set up stipends in a variety of ways in order to grant assistance for those students who come from lower middle class and poor families.

Globally, University education is a significant component of human development. while it not only provides the high level expertise necessary for every labor market but also the Higher Education System train important skills to teachers, nurses, doctors, engineers, civil servants, entrepreneurs, humanists, social scientists, scientists and to a numerous other personnel. These trained individuals develop the aptitude and analytic skills that teach children, drive local economies, lead effective governments, support civil society and make important decisions which affect whole societies.

For interpreting the dream of a knowledge-based economy into reality, the Higher Education in Pakistan and China needs to have merit-oriented, good quality, equitable and efficient higher education as a most crucial instrument. It contributes as well in achieving social goals such as social cohesion, developing civic

responsibility and developing a more tolerant society. therefore, besides traditional functions like crafting new knowledge through research and producing skilled labor force a third one is being added all through the world, that is service to society. Higher Education Commission (HEC) is created for the purpose of serving as an apex body for all matters pertaining to plans, policy, programs, funding, standards and supervision of higher education in the state. The HEC has the duty to prepare guiding principles, policies and priorities for higher education. Higher Education Commission is also accountable for the institution for promoting socioeconomic growth of the country. Moreover, funding of higher education institutions, quality assurance of academic programs and endorsement and the designing of plans for the expansion of higher education.

Chinese Government massive investment in Development and Research has resulted in placing around 100 Chinese Universities in the top 500 Universities of the world, (according to Times Higher Education Ranking (2021)). Shanghai Jiao Tong Universities ranking (2020) and US News and World Report (2020). Sun Yat Sen University, Tsinghua University, Fujian University, Peking University, University of Science and Tech China, Wuhan University, Zhejiang University, Harbin Institute of Technology, Shanghai Jiao Tong University, Nanjing University and Xian Jiao Tong University are ranked among the best 9 Chinese Universities According to QS Ranking . China and Pakistan's academic and research collaboration in past few decades has shown striking growth, in the field of joint collaborative research, graduates studies, research funding, short term placement of students and faculty exchange programs, , organizing Conferences, workshops and Seminars. Moreover, Higher Education Commission considering the impact of academic and information connectivity besides the physical routes, has in time launched the CPEC center at its headquarter. Resultantly, under this program a group of CPEC Universities comprised of more than 50 Universities has been created so far. Furthermore, Knowledge and Research Corridor between the two countries has been established through HEC by submitting a series of PC-1. China Pakistan Joint Research Centre at Quaid-e- Azam University and Academic Collaboration under CPEC association Universities are the two important projects that have started working. In addition to this mega project three more centers will be created with main seat at QUA for Labs for Cryosphere, earth Science and Climate at Marine Sciences Labs at Marine University Karachi and the Karakoram International University Gilgit

Conclusion:

The canvas of bilateral relations between China and Pakistan has expanded after initiating work on CPEC. Therefore, people-to-people connectivity has strengthen from political to economic, cultural to strategic and education to trade that is encouraged through cultural and educational long-medium and short term exchange programs. As Chinese government has planned to set up Pak-China institute of higher education in China for the purpose of granting scholarships. While it links with Higher Education Commission of Pakistan to attract finest students from Pakistan. During the implementation of CPEC and most expectedly after its completion, the prospects of higher education would additionally amplify for Pakistani students in China. Besides, short term educational exchanges and courses would keep enhancing people-to-people contacts, acquaintance with the Chinese language and culture.

Bibliography

- Awan. A.Z. (2020-04-13). *CPEC's biggest impact will be on education sector*. China Daily. <https://global.chinadaily.com.cn/a/202004/13/WS5e93cf3aa3105d50a3d15b83.html>
- Bacha.Umar. (22nd May, 2017). *More Students in Pakistan are learning Chinese today than ever before*. Dawn News. <https://www.dawn.com/news/1333509/more-students-in-pakistan-are-learning-chinese-today-than-ever-before>
- China-Pakistan Economic Corridor: Opportunities and Risks*. (29 June 2018). International Crisis Group. <https://www.crisisgroup.org/asia/south-asia/pakistan/297-china-pakistan-economic-corridor-opportunities-and-risks>
- Cook S. Karen. (2015). *Exchange: Social*. International Encyclopedia of the Social & Behavioral Sciences. Second Edition. Elsevier Ltd. (US), p.482-488.
- Crossman. Ashley. (Aug. 29, 2020). *Understanding Social Exchange Theory*. Thought Co, <https://www.thoughtco.com/social-exchange-theory-3026634>
- Dahlman. J. Carl, Zeng. Z. Douglas , Wang. Shuilin. (2007). *Enhancing China's Competitiveness through Lifelong Learning*. The World Bank. Washington, D.C. p 109.
- Gul, S. (June 19, 2017). *Pakistan China study centre opened in Islamabad*. Islamabad Scene. <https://www.islamabadscene.com/pakistan-china-study-centre-opened-in-islamabad/>
- Higher Education Law of the People's Republic of China, adopted at the Fourth Session of the Standing Committee of the Ninth National People's Congress on August 29, 1998, promulgated by Order No. 7 of the President of the People's Republic of China on August 29, 1998 and take effect on January 1, 1999. p 272.

- Higher Education Law of the People's Republic of China. Laws and Policies.* (July 20, 2009). Ministry of Education, The People's Republic of China. http://en.moe.gov.cn/documents/laws_policies/201506/t20150626_191386.html
- Hutchings, G. (2001). *Modern China: A Guide to a Century of Change.* Harvard University Press. Cambridge, Massachusetts. p 120.
- Homans, G. C. (1958). *Social behavior as exchange.* American Journal of Sociology. p 63.
- Klineberg, O. (1964). *The Human Dimension in International Relations.* New York, NY: Holt, Rinehart and Winston
- Leicht, Alexander, Heiss, Julia, Won Jung Byun. (19-Feb-2018). *Issues and trends in education for sustainable development.* UNESCO Publishing. p 274.
- Mahmood. Khalid. (June 29, 2016). *Overall assessment of the higher education sector (Final Report).* Higher Education Commission (HEC). Pakistan. p 1-2. <https://hec.gov.pk/english/universities/projects/TESP/Documents/FR-Assessment%20HE%20Sector.pdf>
- Memon, G. Rasool. (2007). *Education in Pakistan: The Key Issues, Problems and The New Challenges.* Journal of Management and Social Sciences.
- Miller, A.R. Bratspies .M. R (edt). (2008) . *Progress in International Law.* Martinus Nijhoff Publishers. Boston. p 873.
- National Plan of Action 2013-16 Achieving Universal Primary Education in Pakistan MDG Acceleration Framework.* (August 2013). Education Departments of Provinces and Area Governments Academy of Education Planning and Management (AEPAM), Islamabad UNESCO, Islamabad. p 1.
- Niazi.A.Sajjad. (October 10, 2019). *Confucius Institute at UoS to acquaint students with Chinese language, culture.* Dawn News. <https://www.dawn.com/news/1509935/confucius-institute-at-uos-to-acquaint-students-with-chinese-language-culture>
- Nye, J. S. (2005). *Soft Power and Higher Education.* Forum for the Future of Higher Education Archives. https://www.researchgate.net/deref/https%3A%2F%2Fnet.educause.edu%2Fir%2Flibrary%2Fpdf%2Fffp_iu043.pdf
- Pakistan getting access to Chinese higher education through CPEC.* (May 16, 2021). China-Pakistan Economic Corridor (CPEC). <http://cpecinfo.com/pakistan-getting-access-to-chinese-higher-education-through-cpec>
- Prof Dr Shah. Atta Ullah. (February 6, 2021). *CPEC and China Pakistan Knowledge Corridor.* OP-ED, Daily Times, <HTTPS://DAILYTIMES.COM.PK/720864/CPEC-AND-CHINA-PAKISTAN-KNOWLEDGE-CORRIDOR>
- Redmond V.Mark. (2015). *Social Exchange Theory.* Iowa State University, Digital Repository. p 19.
- Redmond V.Mark. (2015). *Social Exchange Theory.* Iowa State University, Digital Repository. p 04.
- Resources in Education.* (1994). Department of Health, Education, and Welfare, National Institute of Education, Educational Resources Information Centre (ERIC). Volume 29, Issues 3-4. US. p131.
- Saad. A, Xiping,G, Ijaz.M. (2019). *China-Pakistan Economic Corridor and Its Influence on Perceived Economic and Social Goals: Implications for Social Policy Makers.* Sustainability. MDPI, Basel, Switzerland, p 2.
- Safdar.T.M.(June2021). *The Local Roots of Chinese Engagement in Pakistan.* Carnegie Endowment for International Peace. Washington, DC. p 13.
- S.O.Wolf. (20-Jun-2019). *The China-Pakistan Economic Corridor of the Belt and Road Initiative: Concept, Context and Assessment.* Springer, South Asian Democratic Forum (SADF). Belgium.
- The Dakar Framework for Action. (26-28 April 2000). *Education for All: Meeting our Collective Commitments.* World Education Forum. Dakar, Senegal. p 8.
- The Express Tribune. (August 31, 2021). *Pakistanis Studying in China.* <https://tribune.com.pk/story/1950783/1-28000-pakistanis-studying-china>
- What is Social Exchange Theory.* (Friday, April 20, 2018). Tulhan University: the School of Social work.
- Xue. Eryong, Li. Jian. (20-Dec-2020). *Education Poverty Alleviation Policy in China: Concept and Practice.* Springer Natur. Singapore. p 41.
- Yu . Kai, Stith.L. Andrea, Liu.Li, Chen. Huizhong. (2012). *Tertiary Education at a Glance: China.* Sense Publishers, Netherlands.p 23.

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